

The Bitter Principle of Neem Oil. Part I.

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The Neem tree is very plentiful in U. P. and other parts of India. Its seeds contain a high percentage of oil. The oil possesses an objectionable odour and bitter taste. It has got a high reputation for medicinal value from early times. The chemical nature of the oil was first investigated by Warden (*Phar. Indica*, Vol. I. p. 223), who found the oil to contain sulphur and removed the odorous and bitter constituents by shaking the oil with alcohol. Chatterjee (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1917, 5, 656) studied the medicinal properties of the fatty acids derived from the oil. Sen and Chatterjee (*Ind. J. Med. Res.*, 1920, 8, 356) studied in detail and they found the characteristic acid of the oil to be 'margocic acid' belonging to the linoleic acid group (cf. also Ray and Dutt, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 48, 333T). Watson, Chatterjee and Mukherjee (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1923, 42, 387T) worked on the odorous and bitter principle of the oil and ascribed the objectionable odour to the presence of slightly volatile organic sulphur compounds in the oil. The bitterness was also attributed to the presence of resinous acid in the form of ester in the oil.

Watson, Chatterjee and Mukherjee (*loc. cit.*) removed the bitter substance of the oil by alcohol extraction. The bitter alcoholic extract on hydrolysis gave resinous acid which proved to be the mixture of three acids of which two are bitter and one non-bitter. Both the bitter compounds were free from sulphur. During acid hydrolysis they noticed considerable quantity of sulphuretted hydrogen. During the process of purification considerable quantity of free sulphur was obtained with cold benzene.

There is every possible chance that the final sulphur free bitter acids obtained by Watson and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) when contained in the oil in the form of esters, might retain sulphur in the molecule and during the process of purification, the original compounds were decomposed liberating sulphur and sulphuretted hydrogen resulting in the bitter acids actually obtained by them.

In the present investigation, the oil was extracted with hot water and the bitter compounds isolated have been found to differ entirely

from those of Watson and co-workers (*loc. cit.*) in the fact that it contains sulphur in the molecule. It also differs from their compounds by its percentage composition and other physical and chemical properties. This substance exists in the oil chiefly in the form of soluble sodium salt. On being acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid the salt yields yellowish precipitate which turns brown on exposure. The filtrate on concentration gives crystals of sodium chloride. 100 G. of the oil yield approximately 5 g. of the crude product.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Extraction and purification.—The oil was well shaken with hot water in a shaking machine several times (six or seven). The aqueous extract is then separated from the oil in a separating funnel and filtered. The filtrate on evaporation to dryness on a water-bath gave brown product which was redissolved in hot water when a portion remained insoluble (B). The solution (A) containing the Na-salt on filtration was acidified with dilute HCl when yellowish precipitate separated out (D). The solid was then dissolved in acetone and precipitated by dilution with large amount of water slightly acidulated with HCl. It was then dissolved in glacial acetic acid and reprecipitated by dilution with water. It was filtered, washed and was then successively treated with ether and benzene and then with chloroform in which a portion remained undissolved (C). It was quickly filtered in the pump and washed with chloroform. The solution on evaporation gave yellowish solid (E). The process was repeated three or four times to get the product in pure condition.

Both the substances B and D on treatment with chloroform leave a portion undissolved. The portions soluble in chloroform (E) from B and D are also identical as evident from their percentage composition and other physical and chemical properties. The portion insoluble in chloroform was altogether a different substance being free from sulphur. Thus from the crude product two distinct compounds are obtained after purification *viz.*, (1) soluble in chloroform (E) which is bitter and contain sulphur in the molecule and (2) insoluble in chloroform (C) non-bitter and sulphur free.

Action of acids and alkalis on the bitter compound (E).—It readily dissolves in cold dilute solution of sodium carbonate, and ammonia, caustic soda and potash and gives effervescence

with sodium bicarbonate. Dilute acids form brown precipitate from the alkaline solution. Concentrated sulphuric and nitric acids dissolve the substance and on dilution brown precipitate appears. Same reaction is observed with glacial acetic acid; when fused with caustic soda no characteristic reaction of the reagent is observed.

Action of other reagents: Ferric chloride imparts no characteristic coloration. Potassium permanganate is readily decolourised in the cold and bromine decolourises the chloroformic solution of the substance without evolution of hydrobromic acid.

Benzoyl chloride, acetic anhydride, sodium acetate, phenyl hydrazine and Fehling's solution have got no action on the substance.

General properties of the bitter compound (E).—It is yellowish brown in colour. The substance is soluble in alcohol, acetone, glacial acetic acid, chloroform, pyridine and aniline; it is insoluble in water, benzene, ether, carbon disulphide and carbon tetrachloride. The substance in the solid state does not taste bitter but does so when in solution. It contains COOH group and it is unsaturated in character. It contains no free OH but contains methoxy group. It melts with decomposition at 203-205°. (Found: C, 66.61; H, 8.15; S, 3.5. $C_{55}H_{81}O_{13}S$ requires C, 67.2; H, 8.2; S, 3.2 per cent.). Silver salt is prepared in the usual manner. (Found: Ag, 18.05. $C_{55}H_{79}O_{13}SAg_2$ requires Ag, 18.07 per cent.) Molecular wt. (by silver salt) is 982 and 981 (by cryoscopic method). The dibasicity of the acid has also been corroborated by the determination of neutralisation value. Methoxyl group has been determined by Zeisel's method. (Found: OMe, 13.07. $C_{51}H_{69}O_9S(OMe)_4$ requires OMe, 12.55 per cent.).

Bromo derivative is prepared by dissolving the substance (.5g) in alcohol (15 c.c.) and bromine is gradually added. When sufficient quantity of bromine has been added it is left over night. It is then heated on water-bath for 15-20 minutes and then diluted with water when insoluble bromo derivative separates out. It is then filtered, washed with hot water several times and dried. (Found: Br, 13.4. $C_{55}H_{81}O_{13}SBr_2$ requires Br, 14.0 per cent.).

From the experimental results it is thus evident that the bitter compound (E) contains two COOH, four 'OMe' and one double bond in the molecule. The exact constitution has not yet been determined.

The non-bitter compound (C).—This substance is yellowish brown in colour and does not taste bitter in solution. It exists in the

crude state in the proportion of 1:6. It is separated from the bitter substance by chloroform in which it is insoluble. It is soluble in alkalis and acids. Its solubility is the same as the bitter compound but only it is insoluble in chloroform. It decomposes above 270°. On elementary analysis the substance has been found to contain C, H and O only and does not contain sulphur unlike the bitter compound. Complete analysis of this substance was not possible for want of sufficient amount of the substance.

Conclusion.

In conclusion it may be said that the bitterness of the oil is partly due to the presence of the sodium salt of the acid (E) and partly to the presence of free acid which are held in solution in the oil. Complete extraction of the sodium salt from the oil by water does not wholly remove the bitterness of the oil and this residual bitterness is due to the presence of free bitter acid present in oil, it being sparingly soluble in water. That the residual bitterness of the oil is due to the presence of free acid can be easily verified by removing the bitterness by successive treatment of the oil with water and alcohol.

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